

Modelling studies of supercritical fluid extraction of oils from grape and chia seeds

R. M. Filipe^{1,2,*}, J. Coelho^{1,3}, D. Villanueva-Bermejo⁴, T. Fornari⁴, R. Stateva⁵

¹ Instituto Superior de Engenharia de Lisboa, IPL, 1959-007 Lisbon, Portugal; ² Centro de Recursos Naturais e Ambiente (CERENA), IST-UL, 1049-001, Lisbon, Portugal; ³ Centro de Química Estrutural, IST-UL, 1049-001 Lisbon, Portugal; ⁴ Instituto de Investigación en Ciencias de la Alimentación CIAL (CSIC-UAM), 28049 Madrid, España; ⁵ Institute of Chemical Engineering, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia, Bulgaria;

*rfilipe@isel.ipl.pt

This work reports the modelling of the kinetics of supercritical extraction of oils from grape seed samples (obtained from a Portuguese industry), and from two sets of chia seeds - high oil content seeds (HOCS), and underutilized low oil content seeds (LOCS). A rigorous thermodynamic framework was applied to calculate the solubility in the supercritical solvent of the grape and chia seeds oils. The oils, for the purposes of modeling, were represented by triolein. Second order polynomial functions are then fitted to the solubility data and used in the kinetics model of Sovová and Stateva [1] to simulate the extraction curves in gPROMS ModelBuilder [2]. The qualitative and quantitative agreement between the experimental and simulated extraction curves in terms of yields was good ($2\% < \text{AARD} < 9\%$) taking into consideration the very complex nature of the systems examined.

Introduction

Nowadays, increasing attention is drawn to the effective use of waste biomass and vegetal material as renewable resources of high added value compounds with applications in food, cosmetics, pharmaceutical industries, biodiesel production, etc. For example, seed biomass from *Vitis vinifera* L. contains typically (8–15) % (w/w) of oil which is rich in long chain polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) and antioxidants [3,4]. Yet, in many countries the seeds, which represent about (20-25) % of the biomass generated by the wine industry, are considered a disposable material.

Chia (*Salvia hispanica* L.) is also attracting great attention due to its health beneficial properties, especially the seeds, which contain large amounts of oil rich in PUFAs, mainly the omega-3 α -linolenic acid (ALA). Extraction with scCO_2 (SCE) prevents or minimizes the degradation of bioactive compounds and allows obtaining solvent-free products and is currently establishing itself as the viable and eco-friendly alternative to the use of organic solvents. Yet, kinetic data are not abundant, and, particularly for chia seeds oil extraction they are scarce and superficial.

In view of the above, the aim of our work is to model the kinetics of the SCE of oils from industrial grape seeds, obtained directly from a Portuguese industry [5], and from two sets of chia seeds - high oil content (HOCS), and underutilized low oil content (LOCS) seeds, by applying an efficient solution method to a recently introduced kinetics model [1].

Materials and Methods

The SCE of the grape seeds biomass was performed at $T = (313 \text{ and } 333) \text{ K}$ and $p = (20, 30 \text{ and } 40) \text{ MPa}$ and flow rates of (1.8, 2.3 and 2.8) $\text{g}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ of CO_2 . Figure 1 shows the cumulative extraction curves plotted to assess the effect of pressure, temperature and flow rate in the process of SCE, as well as the simulated profiles.

The SCEs from LOCS were carried out at two pressures (25 and 45 MPa), two temperatures (313 and 333 K), 40 $\text{g}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ of CO_2 flow rate and 240 min extraction time. The extractions of

HOCS were performed at 45 MPa, 313 K and several CO_2 flow rates (27, 40 and 54) $\text{g}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, which represent a CO_2 -to-seed ratio of 50, 70 and 100, respectively). Figure 2 shows the experimental kinetic curves and the simulated profiles for the SCE of chia oil from LOCS.

Figure 1. Experimental (symbols) and simulated extraction curves (lines) at a scCO_2 flow rate of 1.8 $\text{g}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ at different pressures and temperatures for grape seeds.

Figure 2. Experimental (symbols) and simulated extraction curves (lines) at a scCO_2 flow rate of 40 $\text{g}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ at different pressures and temperatures for LOCS.

The grape and chia seed oils are very complex mixtures of mainly triacylglycerols (TAGs) with minor amounts of other

compounds. For the purpose of modelling, they have to be represented by model TAGs. Thus, following the results of the composition analyses, the grape seed oil is represented by triolein [5].

The most suitable model representative of chia seed oil is trilinolenin. However, taking into consideration two very important issues, namely: *i*) lack of any experimental information on the VLE of trilinolenin+scCO₂; *ii*) total lack of data (both experimental and estimated) on the thermophysical properties of trilinolenin, we chose triolein as the TAG to represent the chia seed oil.

To calculate the solubility of the TAGs in the scCO₂, the VLE of the two component (triolein+CO₂) system should be modelled, which requires a reliable thermodynamic model. In our study we apply the predictive Soave-Redlich-Kwong (PSRK) cubic EoS [6], with the triolein properties estimated by us.

In order to calculate the yield and composition of the oil extracts at the experimental temperatures, pressures and scCO₂ flow rates for the grape and chia seeds, the novel model of Sovova and Stateva [1] was applied. Although the model was developed for multicomponent extraction, it remains valid for a single component system.

This model considers homogeneous concentration in the extractor at both solid and fluid phases and assumes that the extracts are located on the surface of the solid particles. This assumption allows neglecting internal diffusion, which is compatible with finely ground substrates where the diffusion path in the particles is short and the extract is easily accessible, resulting in negligible internal mass transfer resistance.

The model was deployed, validated and executed using gPROMS ModelBuilder [2], an equation-oriented modelling and optimisation platform for steady-state and dynamic systems. gPROMS offers an integrated framework where all the tasks can be performed within the same environment, with

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the funding received from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 778168. J.A.P. Coelho and R. M. Filipe are thankful for the financial support from Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, Portugal, under projects UID/QUI/00100/2013 and UID/ECI/04028/2013.

References

- [1] H. Sovová, R. P. Stateva, *Industrial and Engineering Chemistry Research*, 54 (2015) 4861-4870.
- [2] gPROMS ModelBuilder Documentation. Process Systems Enterprise Ltd., London, 2018.
- [3] S. Bail, G. Stuebiger, S. Krist, H. Unterweger, G. Buchbauer, *Food Chemistry* 108 (2008) 1122-1132.
- [4] L. Fernandes, S. Casal, R. Cruz, J.A. Pereira, E. Ramalhosa, *Food Research International*, 50 (2013) 161.
- [5] J. Coelho, R. Filipe, M. Robalo, R. Stateva, *Journal of Supercritical Fluids* (in press). doi: 10.1016/j.supflu.2017.12.008
- [6] T. Holderbaum, J. Gmehling, *Fluid Phase Equilibria*. 70 (1991) 251-265.

embedded solvers that can usually complete the simulations without further user input if a complete and well formulated model, with the adequate initial conditions, is provided.

Results and Conclusions

Using gPROMS Modelbuilder parameter estimation, the partition coefficient (K) was estimated for all the cases. The maximum oil content corresponding to monolayer adsorption (w_1) was also estimated for the chia seeds case. gPROMS uses a maximum likelihood parameter estimation problem and attempts to determine values for the uncertain physical and variance model parameters that maximize the probability that the mathematical model will predict the measurement values obtained from the experiments.

In order to compare the fitting accuracy obtained with other works, a standard deviation measure, the absolute average relative deviation, AARD, was also calculated after parameter estimation using Eq. 1, where N is the total number of experimental points, and e_i^{exp} and e_i^{est} - the i -th experimental and estimated point, respectively.

$$AARD = \frac{100}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{|e_i^{exp} - e_i^{est}|}{e_i^{exp}} \quad (1)$$

The AARD values obtained ranged from (2 to 9) % for the grape seeds and LOCS, and from (2 to 7) % for HOCS, which may be considered as a good agreement taking into consideration the very complex nature of the systems under study.

The new modelling approach applied incorporates in a rigorous way the interplay between phase equilibria (solubility) and kinetics, and the results obtained demonstrate that albeit the simplifications introduced there is a good qualitative and quantitative agreement between the experimental and calculated extraction yields at the SCEs operating conditions examined.